

Gendered Food Mapping of Fried Sweetpotato in Kano State, Nigeria

Understanding the Drivers of Trait Preferences and the Development of Multi-user RTB Product Profiles, WP1

Kano State, Nigeria, 31st October 2019

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This report has been written in the framework of RTBfoods project.

To be cited as:

Ali ABDULLAHI, Reuben Tendo SSALI, Souleimane ADEKAMBI, Samuel Edgar TINYIRO, (2023). *Gendered Food Mapping of Fried Sweetpotato in Kano State, Nigeria. Understanding the Drivers of Trait Preferences and the Development of Multi-user RTB Product Profiles, WP1.* Kano State, Nigeria: RTBfoods Field Scientific Report, 22p.

Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this manual, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes. Written consent (signature) was systematically sought from sensory panelists and from consumers participating in activities.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the RTBfoods project <https://rtbfoods.cirad.fr>, through a grant OPP1178942: Breeding RTB products for end user preferences (RTBfoods), to the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), Montpellier, France, by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF).

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Final validation by:

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27/01/23

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ABSTRACT

The study took place in Kano state in the Sudan savannah agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. More specifically in Bagwai and Garko local governments where four communities were selected namely; Gogori and Liringo (Bagwai), Kafin-Chiri and Garin-Ali (Garko). These areas are renowned for having a high concentration of sweet potato producers, processors and consumers. Four Key Informant Interviews (KII), Eight-disaggregated Focus Group Discussions (FGD), Individual Interviews (II) with 40 community members and Six Market Interviews (MI) with key individuals or groups were conducted. The most prevalent farming practice by men and women in Bagwai was monocropping while in Garko it was intercropping. Sweetpotato was ranked the most important crop in all the communities during the dry season. However in the rainy season, sorghum took precedence. In addition, sweetpotato was grown by at least 80% of the people sampled. Activities involved in production of sweetpotato in these communities were gender-specific, for example women were mostly involved in planting the vine cuttings and harvesting. The respondents indicated that they had accessed new sweetpotato varieties in the past 10-20 years; Gogori had received Dan-Izala, those in Liringo it was Dan-Madagali and Dan-Izala while for Garun-Ali it was the variety Dan Barnawa. The most common varieties grown at the time of the study were; Dan-Madagali, Dan-Izala, Dan-Bakalori, Dan-China, Dan-Barnawa and Dan-Batsari. Important characteristics of sweetpotato spanned agronomic, post-harvest, sensory and market attributes such as; mealiness, high yield, high price, big tubers and early maturity.

Key Words: fried, sweetpotato, gender, food mapping, cropping system, varieties, characteristics

1 INTRODUCTION

Sweetpotato (*Ipomoea batatas*) is a member of morning glory family (*Convolvulaceae*) which originated from Latin America (Low *et al.*, 2009), producing edible storage roots, and leaves. The crop is cultivated throughout tropical and warm temperate regions wherever there is sufficient water to support its growth. Sweetpotato is ranked number 7th among world major food crops (Nwauzor and Ezulike, 2005), and is also ranked 4th among the four major root and tuber crops in Nigeria (APMEU, 1996). Nigerian production output has put the country as the number two largest producer of sweet potato in Africa and the third largest producer in the world with China leading followed by Uganda (FAO, 2004).

Sweetpotato can yield large amounts of energy-rich nutritious foods during relatively short cropping seasons. According to Degras (2003), sweet potato is composed of 22-44% dry matter, 50-75% starch, 6.0-15.0% sugars, 1.7-5.3% proteins, 0.5-0.9% fibres and 0.2-0.5% phenols. The crop is rich in antioxidant and has also been identified as having anti-aging nutrients. The orange fleshed sweet potato (OFSP) in particular is different from other varieties in having a significant amount of beta carotene, a precursor to vitamin A.

In an attempt to identify some potential use of roots of orange-fleshed sweet potato genotypes in the production of β -carotene rich chips in Nigeria, Ukpabi (2012) emphasised that most of the sweet potato landraces in Nigeria have white fleshed roots with negligible amount of the pro-vitamin A pigment. In earlier findings, Ijeh and Ukpabi (2004) had shown that a popular local yellow fleshed landrace (known as Ex-Igbariam) has appreciable but relatively limited quantity of β -carotene (3 μ g/g fresh root sample).

Sweet potatoes are most commonly used for human consumption, animal feed, and diverse industrial uses. Sweet potatoes are usually consumed fresh but prepared in many different ways. Most commonly, the fresh root is peeled and boiled, roasted, or fried into chips (fries). The leaves are often boiled and incorporated into soups and stews or stir fried with chili and minced dried shrimps. Sweet potatoes are also commonly fed to infants and young children.

Despite increase in production and nutritional importance of the crop, its production is faced with many constraints in Nigeria, among which are the menaces of insect pests (sweet potato weevil *Cylas formicarius*, *C. puncticollis* and *C. brunneus*, leaf-eating beetles *Aspidomorpha* spp. and several species of caterpillar), diseases (Soft or woolly rot caused by bacterium *Erwinia chrysanthemi* or the fungus *Rhizopus stolonifer*, charcoal rot caused by *Monilochaetes infusans*), storage, processing and marketing problems.

Sometimes there are clear differences in the characteristics preferred by user groups that follow product/consumption profiles, but other times it is more complex. Different users of sweet potato may live in the same household, have different interests with how it is used and what products are made. This can result in multiple and, perhaps, contrasting preferences that vary according to the user's role in the food chain, meaning that the input and decision-making roles of different users is of primary importance to crop breeding.

Preferences for certain characteristics stem from broader socio-economic and gender dynamics, which are in turn an integral part of understanding the choice and use of sweet potato. Men, women, boys and girls play different roles in RTB food chains, and differ in their access to, perceptions of risk for, and ability to decide on use of both local and improved sweet potato varieties. In addition, consumers have their own sets of sensory preferences linked to different varieties, and consumers may have different preferences based on their background, gender and location.

However, there is a gap in knowledge of preferences for sweet potato among different user groups, particularly food processors, retailers and consumers, and diversity within user groups. Furthermore, there is little known about how gender relations and norms influence and result in preferred characteristics, along with varietal uses.

1.1 Objectives of fried sweetpotato gendered mapping

- Understand who is producing, processing, selling and consuming fried sweet potato from a gendered perspective.
- Understand the multiple uses of fried sweet potato and possible trade-offs between uses
- Identify the quality characteristics and descriptors by stakeholder group (e.g. producers, processors) and demand segment (e.g. rural consumers).
- Understand how gender influences preferences and prioritisation for characteristics

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Description of study areas

Kano state is situated in the Sudan savannah agro ecological zone of Nigeria located between latitude 9° 30" and 10° 33" to 12° 37" North and longitudes 7° 34" to 9° 25" East. The state occupies a total land area of about 42,582.8Km square. The state is bordered to the west and northwest by Katsina State, to the east and northeast by Jigawa state, to the south by Bauchi state and the southwest by Kaduna state (Kano State Government, 2004). The state has 44 local government areas with a total land area of 42,582.8km square out of which agricultural land is 30,684.8Km square, while forest and grazing land has 11,898 km square (Kano State Government, 2004). The population of Kano State in 2013 was estimated to be 11,354,255 people, male 5,861,407 and female 5,492,848. The major tribes are Hausa and Fulani ethnic group but other ethnic groups inhabiting the state include almost all major and minor tribes in Nigeria. Other national from different population is put at 7 percent of the total population (Kano State Government, 2004).

The climate of the study area is tropical dry climate with a mono modal rainfall distribution averaging 600mm per annum with most rains occurring between May and September. Air humidity is high during the wet season and very low during the dry season. Average temperature is 29°C with minimum temperature of 15°C occurring from November to February and highest temperature of 39°C occurring in March and April (Olafin and Tanko, 2002). The main soil type is developed from wind-blown sands derived from acid crystalline rocks of a basement complex. The soils are light, freely graining and loamy which have proved highly amenable to intensive cultivation. Generally, the highest elevation in Kano State is found towards the south-western tip of the State. It is about 1,200m above sea level, this decreases as one move northwards with 450m above sea level. Natural vegetation of the state is the savannah type, although this has given way to cultural vegetation. Most of the area is contained within the Sudan savannah.

2.2 Defining the segments

- Basis for selection: High concentration of sweet potato producers, processors and consumers.
- More women involved in the production, processing and trading of sweet potato in these areas.
- Differences of the two locations (North Senatorial zone – Bagwai and South Senatorial Zone – Garko)
- Homogenous cultural settings.

Production, processing and marketing of sweet potato are grouped according to geography and segment these activities accordingly. The segmentation of sweet potato in this respect are performed into regions or zones.

Regions in Nigeria – Kano and Kwara.

Zones – Bagwai – (Kano North) and Garko – (Kano South)

To generate data for all segments of sweet potato value chain according to regions/zones. Sweet Potato product profiling at various regions/zones, inter-regional and inter-zonal comparisons, becomes more convenient.

2.3 Activities in the study areas

There were four activities that took place in four rural communities where people grew, processed and consumed sweet potato. These were:

- Four Key Informant Interviews (KII) with community leadership in four Communities: Gogori and Liringo (Bagwai), Kafin-Chiri and Garin-Ali (Garko).
- Eight-disaggregated Focus Group Discussions (FGD) with people who produce, process and consume Sweet Potato in the four communities above. The FGDs specifically provide information on products, gender roles and social segments, processing steps and equipment, characteristics and descriptors that can be probed in further in IIs.
- Individual Interviews (II) with 40 community members in the four communities who process the product (and produce the crop, if possible) in the community, conducted by a food scientist and gender specialist. The IIs provides individual/household level description of preferred characteristics and priorities at different stages of product processing, household decision making, and trade-offs.
- Six Market Interviews (MI) with key individuals or groups involved in marketing and trading activities.

3 FINDINGS: SOCIAL-ECONOMIC CONTEXT AND PRODUCT PREFERENCES

3.1 Social segmentation and livelihoods

From the focus group discussions, the participants in different communities had different perceptions on the wealth categorization, such variations were also found within the communities (Table 1). During the focus group discussions, the two communities in Garko went further to disaggregate the wealth category on gender perspectives. Female indicators of wealth category were basically multiple trading or businesses, number of farmlands owned and the ability of the wealthy individuals to send more trucks of sweet potato to other markets.

Table 1 : Social segments

Local Govt. Area	Community Name	Social Segments (%)
Bagwai	Gogori	Ethnicity: Hausa (80%) Fulani (20%). Wealth: Very poor (15%), Poor (45%), Moderate wealth (35%) Very wealthy (5%) Household headship: female headed (18%), child headed (7%), male headed (75%) Wealthy category: Family size, Ability to purchase more fertiliser, Ability to send more than 10 trucks of sweet potato to market, number of houses owned, farming different types of crops.

Local Govt. Area	Community Name	Social Segments (%)
	Liringo	Ethnicity: Hausa (90%) Fulani (10%). Wealth: Very poor (2%), Poor (68%), Moderate wealth (20%) Very wealthy (10%) Household headship: female headed (10%), child headed (5%), male headed (85%) Wealthy category: Multiple occupation, Nature of houses, Ability to send 5 trucks of sweet potato to markets.
Garko	Kafin-Chiri	Ethnicity: Hausa (95%) Fulani (5%). Household headship: female headed (15%), child headed (5%), male headed (80%)
		Female perception of Wealth: Very poor (30%), Poor (10%), Moderate wealth (50%) Very wealthy (10%) Wealthy category: Multiple trading, nature of farming.
		Male perception of Wealth: Very poor (5%), Poor (20%), Moderate wealth (70%) Very wealthy (5%) Wealthy category: Size of farmland (e.g.5ha), Capital of One Million Naira, 5 Heads of Cattle, Fine house and Different sources of income.
	Garin-Ali	Ethnicity: Hausa (85%) Fulani (15%). Wealth: Very poor (10%), Poor (37%), Moderate wealth (45%) Very wealthy (8%) Household headship: female headed (7%), child headed (3%), male headed (90%)
		Female perception of Wealth: Very poor (20%), Poor (30%), Moderate wealth (50%) Very wealthy (0%) Wealthy category: Number of farmlands, number of wives, nature of house
		Male perception of Wealth: Very Poor (5%), Poor (10%), Moderate wealth (70%) Wealthy (10%) Very Wealthy (5%). Wealthy category: Size of farmland, Heads of Cattle, Mechanisation and Ability to own a truck.

The inhabitants of these communities were predominantly Hausa and few Fulani pastoralists. However, there were other tribes from Eastern part of Nigeria that settled in these communities before and their major livelihood activities were; medicine and provision stores. They did not involve themselves in farming activities. They resettled in larger communities like Bagwai, Bichi, Shanono and Gwarzo.

There were other tribes (Tiv and Angas) from Benue and Kogi States that were temporarily settling in these communities for fishing, hunting of rodents in the bush. There were people from different parts of the country that came to these communities during the harvesting periods for the purchase of sweet potatoes. Some of them settled for some days to make large purchases before moving out of the communities.

The major livelihood activities in these communities were virtually the same, except Gogori where the community according to the leadership is well known in pots making, which was predominantly performed by female in this community (Table 2). Livelihood activities in these communities are gender-specific, with some activities been predominantly performed by males and some by females.

Table 2 : Livelihoods activities with gender perspectives

Local Area	Govt.	Male/Female and Community name	FGD the	Major Livelihood Activities	Gender (Who perform which activity?)	
Bagwai	Women Gogori		FGD,	Farming	All	
				Livestock Management Practices	All	
				Marketing sweet potato	All	
				Carpentry	Older and young men	
				Bricklaying	Older and young men	
				Pottery	Older women and young female	
				Selling cooked foods	All	
				Tailoring	Older men and women	
				Men FGD, Gogori.	Farming	All
				Trading Livestock and grains	Older and young men	
				Marketing sweet potato	All	
				Carpentry	Older and young men	
				Bricklaying	Older and young men	
				Fishing	Older and young men	
				Tailoring	Older men and women	
	Women Liringo	FGD,	Farming	Male and Female		
	Livestock Management	All				
	Trading of Agricultural produce	Older and young men				
	Bricklaying	Older and young men				
	Fishing	Older and young men				
	Smiting	Male				
	Selling cooked foods	Older and young women				
	Tailoring	All				
	Grinding vegetables (tomato, pepper) and beans	Older women and young female				
	Grinding grains	Young men.				
	Men FGD, Liringo	Farming	Male and Female			
	Livestock Management	All				
Trading of Agricultural produce	Older and young men					
Fishing	Older and young men					
Bricklaying	Older and young men					
Carpentry	Older and young men					
Welding	Older and young men					
Smiting	Older and young men					
Tailoring	All					
Frog catching	Older and young men (Tiv tribe from Benue State).					
Rodents hunting	Older and young men (Angas tribe)					
Garko	Women Kafin-Chiri		FGD,	Farming	All	
				Trading Livestock and grains	Older and young men	
				Fishing	Older and young men	
	Men FGD, Kafin-Chiri.			Kafin-Chiri.	Bricklaying	Older and young men
					Selling cooked foods	All
					Farming	All
				Trading	Older and young men	

Local Area	Govt.	Male/Female and Community name	FGD the	Major Livelihood Activities	Gender (Who perform which activity?)
				Fishing	Older and young men
				Husbandry	Older and young men
				Hunting	Older and young men
				Bricklaying	Older and young men
				Carpentry	Older and young men
				Biking	Older and young men
				Commercial Driving	Older and young men
		Women	FGD,	Farming	All
		Garun-Ali.		Rice Milling	All
				Tailoring	All
				Selling cooked foods	All
				Trading of goods	Older and young men
				Livestock rearing and selling	All
		Men	FGD,	Farming	All
		Ali	Garun-	Trading farm produce	Older and young men
				General trading	All
				Building	Older and young men
				Mechanics	Older and young men
				Smiting	Older and young men
				Fishing	Older and young men
				Butchers	Older and young men
				Tailoring	All
				Food processing	Older women and young female

Fishing was a common livelihood activity in all these communities, which was due to the water bodies around these communities. The water bodies in addition to fishing support the production of sweet potato and other vegetable crops in the dry season. Frog catching was another activity supported by the presence of water bodies, performed mostly by some people from Benue State. The fishing activities attract other ethnic groups from Benue and Sokoto States. Their settlements in these communities were mostly on temporary basis.

In virtually all the communities, very poor and very wealthy individuals were generally low (Table 3). There were similarities among the wealth categories in all the communities. Very poor individuals were considered as those with no farmlands and inability to feed their families, 3 meals a day. Moreover, in some communities like Garun-Ali and Kafin-Chiri, the poor and very poor, were those unable to send their children to school, but to street hawking.

Table 3 : Wealth categories

Local Govt. Area	Community Name	Wealth Categories
Bagwai	Gogori	Wealth: Very poor (15%) = Wage labourers, No farmland, Not educated, Not engaged in any livelihood activity, Poor (45%) = Use hired farmlands, wage labourer, Not educated, Moderate wealth (35%) = Farmlands, Own a house, Civil servant, engaged in small business, Educated Very wealthy (5%) = Large scale business, own some farmlands, Own some houses, Vehicles.

Local Govt. Area	Community Name	Wealth Categories
	Liringo	Wealth: Very poor (2%) = Depending on others for food, No farmlands, Not household head, Poor (68%) = Wage labourer, Could hardly have foods for three days, One small farmland, Moderate wealth (20%) = Store foods for a month, has more than one farmland, own a house, has a motorcycle, Very wealthy (10%) = Multiple occupation, Nature of houses, Ability to send 5 trucks of sweet potato to markets
Garko	Kafin-Chiri	Female perception of Wealth: Very poor (30%); Depending on others for food, No farmlands, Poor (10%) = Children involved in street hawking, inadequate foods, one and small farmland. Petty trading, Moderate wealth (50%) = Sending children to school, more than one farmland, Very wealthy (10%): Multiple trading, nature of farming.
		Male perception of Wealth: Very poor (5%) = No farmland, no food to eat every day, Poor (20%) = One small farmland, do not own a house, wage labourer, Moderate wealth (70%) = May be civil servant, may have tertiary education, have more than one farmland, Own a house. Very wealthy (5%) = Size of farmland (e.g.5ha), Capital of One Million Naira, 5 Heads of Cattle, Fine house and Different sources of income.
	Garin-Ali	Female perception of Wealth: Very poor (20%)= No farmland, Do not own a house Poor (30%) = wage labourer, one small farmland, sending children to sale foods, Moderate wealth (50%) = have enough food, some level of education, Very wealthy (0%) = Number of farmlands, number of wives, nature of house
		Male perception of Wealth: Very Poor (5%),= No farmland, not cook 3 times in a day, Poor (10%) = Moderate wealth (70%) = Own at least one house, has more than one farmland. Wealthy (10%) Very Wealthy (5%) = Size of farmland, Heads of Cattle, Mechanisation and Ability to own a truck.

However, there were differences in those communities in the perceptions of men and women as individuals considered to be wealthy or moderately wealthy. Education was an indicator for considering someone to be wealthy, as perceived by both males and females participated in Focus group discussions.

3.2 Farming practices and social segmentation

The most prevalent farming practice by men and women in Bagwai was monocropping (**Table 4**). More so, those in Gogori indicated that they also practiced intercropping. However, respondents in Garko mostly practiced intercropping.

Table 4 : Farming practices

Local Govt. Area	Male/Female and the Community name	FGD	Farming Practices	People Practice	Who
Bagwai	Women FGD, Gogori		Monocropping (Ridges)	Men	
			Intercropping (Heaps) Store long in the soil and the roots are bigger (Intercropped with Hibiscus, planted at the same time.	Men	
	Men FGD, Gogori		Monocropping (Ridges)	Men	
			Intercropping (Heaps) (Intercropped with Hibiscus, planted at the same time	Men	
	Women FGD, Liringo		Monocropping (Both seasons) All the practices.	All	Young female, Young men and Men
	Men FGD, Liringo		Monocropping (All the practices).	Men, male	Young
Garko	Women FGD, Kafin-Chiri		Intercropping (Rainy season with sorghum, Groundnut and Cowpea (Ridges)	Young female, Men	
			Intercropping (Dry season with Carrot, Onion) (Heaps)	Young female, Men	
	Men FGD, Kafin-Chiri		Intercropping (Rainy season with maize and sorghum, (Ridges)	Youth, Adults and Women	
			Intercropping (Dry season with Carrot, Onion) (Heaps)	Youth, Adults and women	
	Women FGD, Garun-Ali		Intercropping (Rainy season with sorghum, soybean and Cowpea (Ridges)	Young and middle-aged men.	
			Intercropping (Dry season) (Heaps)	Young and middle-aged	
	Men FGD		Intercropping (rainy season)	All	

3.2.1 Important crops in the community

From **Table 5**, it was found that sorghum was ranked the most important crop in all the communities among males and females, which was followed by sweet potato. Maize and Millet were ranked 3rd and 4th important crops, respectively. The probable reason was mainly how the communities considered the use of grains for home consumption. However, the ranking was only for rainy season not for dry season. The ranking for dry season is presumably in favour of sweet potato in these communities as an important crop grown in this season (Table 6).

Table 5 : Important crops in the community

Crop importance	Women	Men
1	Sorghum	Sorghum
2	Sweet Potato	Sweet Potato
3	Maize	Maize
4	Millet Rice	Millet

Sweet potato ranks first when it's in season. Considered as cash crop, generates more money in these communities than any other thing.

Women FGDs in Garun-Ali nicknamed Sweet potato as; '**JUST WAIT**'.

Some women in the same discussions emphasised that;

*'if you want to marry/give out your daughter to another man, you should grow **SWEET POTATO**'*

Table 6 : Important crops in the rural communities

BAGWAI				
Crop Importance	Gogori		Liringo	
	Women	Men	Women	Men
	Rainy Season	Rainy Season	Rainy Season	Rainy Season
1	Sweet potato	Sorghum	Maize	Sweet potato
2	Maize	Sweet potato	Sweet Potato	Maize
3	Sorghum	Maize	Sorghum	Millet
4	Millet	Millet		Sorghum
5	Rice	Groundnut		Pearl millet
6	Sesame	Cowpea		Cowpea
7		Pearl millet		Soybean
8		Soybean		Cotton
9				Sesame
	Dry Season	Dry Season	Dry Season	Dry Season
1	Sweet potato	Sweet potato	Sweet potato	Sweet potato
2	Groundnut	Carrot	Maize	Garden egg
3	Cassava	Onion	Sorghum	Chilli pepper
4	Soybean	Tomato		Onion
5	Cotton	Garden egg		Cassava
6	Cowpea			
GARKO				
Crop Importance	Kafin-Chiri		Garun-Ali	
	Women	Men	Women	Men
	Rainy Season	Rainy Season	Rainy Season	Rainy Season
1	Sorghum	Sorghum	Sweet potato	Sweet potato
2	Groundnut	Maize	Sorghum	Sorghum
3	Cowpea	Millet	Rice	Groundnuts
4	Sweet potato	Groundnut	Millet	Millet
5		Cowpea	Groundnut	Rice
6		Pearl millet	Pearl millet	Pearl millet
7		Soybean		Soybean
8				Cowpea
	Dry Season	Dry Season	Dry Season	Dry Season
1	Sweet potato	Carrots	Maize	Carrots
2	Carrot	Onions	Soybean	Onions
3	Onion	Sweet potato	Cowpea	Cabbage
4		Tomatoes		Lettuce
5		Garden eggs		Tomatoes
6		Chilli pepper		Okra

Sweetpotato and maize were identified as important for income while millet and sorghum were for home consumption (Table 7). All crops were important for men, women and youth with the exception of maize (men and women).

Table 7: Reasons why the crop is important and for who

Crop	Reasons why the crop is important	People for who the crop is important
Sweet potato	Generates income (Women's FGD Liringo)	Men, Women and Youth (All FGDs).
Maize	Home consumption and sales (Men's FGD Liringo)	Men and Women (All FGDs)
Millet	Home consumption (Men's FGD Liringo)	Men, Women and Youth (All FGDs)
Sorghum	Home consumption (Men's FGD Liringo)	Men, Women and Youth (All FGDs)

3.3 Crop in Focus

Gender Perspectives of Sweet Potato Producers

Sweetpotato was grown by at least 80% of the people in Gogori, Liringo, Kafin-Chiri and Garun-Ali (Table 8). Respondents indicated that more men grew sweetpotato compared to women however in Garun-Ali, this was evenly balanced.

Table 8: Sweetpotato growing

Community	Proportion (%) of people in the community who grow the crop	Proportion (%) of the crop that the average household uses for making the product
Gogori	90% (70% Men and 20% Women)	80%
Liringo	80%	65%
Kafin-Chiri	90% (30% - 35% - Women)	70%
Garun-Ali	80% (40% Women)	70%

Activities involved in production of sweet potato in these communities were gender-specific, with some activities being predominantly performed by males and others by females. According to the community leaders interviewed, virtually all the production activities were performed by males (young and old), with young males performing more activities than their older counterparts. The production activities mostly performed by females were planting the vine cuttings and harvesting, which according to them were not hard to do.

The cropping systems vary with geographical location. Communities in North Zone, according to the community leaders intercropped in the dry season, while those in the South Zone intercropped in the rainy season (Table 9).

Table 9: Growing sweetpotato in the communities

Community	Cropping system	Seasonality	Planting time	Harvesting time	Remarks
Gogori	Monocropping	Rainy	Late May-July	September, ending - November	
	Intercropping	Dry	October, ending	January - February	Intercropped with Hibiscus
Liringo	Monocropping	Rainy	Late May-July	September, ending - November	

Community	Cropping system	Seasonality	Planting time	Harvesting time	Remarks
	Intercropping	Dry	October, ending	January - February	Intercropped with Maize
Kafin-Chiri	Monocropping	Dry	October, ending	January - February	
	Intercropping	Rainy	Late May-July	September, ending - November	Intercropped with Sorghum
Garun-Ali	Monocropping	Dry	October, ending	January - February	
	Intercropping	Rainy	Late May-July	September, ending - November	Intercropped with Sorghum and Soybean

In Garun-Ali, the planting in the last 4 – 5 years was in 3 stages; June, August and September. 80% - 90% of the men farmers in these communities grow sweet potato. 50% - 60% of the women farmers in these communities grow sweet potato. But all the activities are carried out by either their husbands or male sons. In Gogori -Rich farmers – 40% and Poor farmers – 60%.

For those not cultivating sweetpotato, various reasons were put forward depending on the location (Table 10). Communities in Kafin-Chiri and Garun-Ali indicated pest and diseases while in Liringo it was failed yields in the previous season and decline in price for the Gogori community.

Table 10: Reasons for not planting sweet potato;

Community	Reasons for not planting sweet potato
Gogori	Declined in price Having only one farm
Liringo	Failure in yield in the previous season
Kafin-Chiri	Disease and pest attack (Sankara)
Garun-Ali	Disease and pest attack (Ebola)

Access to new sweet potato varieties

New sweetpotato varieties accessed in the last 10 – 20 years are shown in Table 11. In recent years, the community in Gogori had received Dan-Izala, those in Liringo it was Dan-Madagali and Dan-Izala while for Garun-Ali it was the variety, Dan Barnawa.

Table 11: Access to new sweetpotato varieties

Community	Access to new sweet potato varieties
Gogori	Dan-Dakata and Dan-Bakalori - last 15 years Only one variety (Dan-Izala) was introduced in the last 10 years
Liringo	Red Dan-Bakalori was introduced last 20 years. Dan-Madagali and Dan-Izala introduced last 5 years from Sokoto.
Garun-Ali	Old varieties – Dan-Bakaloji, Dan-Zaria and Dan-China. New variety – Dan-Barnawa – Introduced by PhD research student from Bayero University

Factors limiting use of improved variety

The main causes of limited use of improved varieties in the communities were; no access to vines in subsequent years, late maturity, disease and pest attack and their lack of mealiness.

Consumption patterns of Sweet Potato in the Communities;

At least 70% of the sweetpotatoes grown in the communities were for sale (Table 12).

Table 12: Proportion of sweetpotatoes sold

Community	Proportion of sweetpotatoes sold
Gogori	Fried – 7 out of 10 of the sweet potatoes grown are sold. Boiled – 8 out of 10 of the sweet potatoes grown are sold.
Liringo	7 out of 10 are sold.
Kafin-Chiri and Garun-Ali	9 out of 10 are sold.

Sweet potato was consumed mostly during rainy season and fasting periods. During these periods the products were consumed daily. This trend has not changed in the last five years.

3.3.1 Varieties of Sweet Potato Grown

Table 13 shows the sweetpotato varieties grown in the communities. The varieties grown across Gogori and Liringo were; Dan-Madagali, Dan-Izala and Dan-Bakalori. These were grown by both men and women.

Table 13 : Varieties grown in the community and ranking in order of preference

Importance	Gogori		Liringo	
	Men's FGD	Women's FGD	Men's FGD	Women's FGD
1	Dan-Madagali	Dan-izala	Dan-Madagali	Dan-Madagali
2	Dan-Izala	Dan-Madagali	Dan-Izala	Dan-Izala
3	Silba	Dan-Bakalori	Dan-Bakalori	Dan-Bakalori
4	Dan-Bakalori	Silba	Dan-Dakata	Dan-Dakata
Importance	Kafin- Chiki		Garun-Ali	
	Men's FGD	Women's FGD	Men's FGD	Women's FGD
1	Dan-China	Dan-China	Dan-Bakalori	Dan-China
2	Dan-Barnawa	Dan-Barnawa	Dan-China	Dan-Barnawa
3	Dan-Batsari	Dan-Batsari	Dan-Batsari	Dan-Bakalori
4	Dan-Bakalori	Dan-Bakalori	Dan-Zaria	Dan-Batsari
5	Dan-Zaria	Dan-Zaria	Dan-Barnawa	
6	King J.			
7	Shonekan (MD)			

In Kafin- Chiki and Garun-Ali they were; Dan-China, Dan-Barnawa, Dan-Batsari and Dan-Bakalori albeit prioritised differently between the communities. Dan-Bakalori was cultivated in all regions by both men and women.

Important characteristics of sweetpotato spanned agronomic, post-harvest, sensory and market attributes (Table 14). Of highest importance to respondents in Gogori and Liringo was mealiness except for the Gogori men for whom high yield was top. More so, high yield and price were important for both men and women in Gogori. Big tubers were priority for men and women in Liringo.

Table 14 : Most important characteristics of sweet potato in order of preference

Importance	Gogori		Liringo	
	Women's FGD	Men's FGD	Women's FGD	Men's FGD
1	Mealiness	High Yield	Mealiness	Mealiness
2	High price	High price	Big tubers	Early maturity
3	High yield	Disease resistant	Skin condition (Smooth)	Big tubers
4			Milky water	Good taste
5				
Importance	Kafin- Chiki		Garun-Ali	
	Women's FGD	Men's FGD	Women's FGD	Men's FGD
1	Not affected by insects	Mealiness	Early maturity	Good storage
2	Early maturing	Good oil flavour	High yield	Early maturing
3	Low moisture content	Light, Uniform colour	Mealiness	Big tubers
4	Store for long		White colour	Bright Colour
5				

Early maturity was an important characteristic across the communities in Kafin-Chiki and Garun-Ali. Only the men in Kafin-Chiki did not have this as a priority characteristic.

3.3.2 Uses of Sweet Potato

Products from sweetpotato included fried, boiled, roasted and dried sweetpotato (Table 15). Mealiness was a key characteristic for men and women across the communities for fried and boiled sweetpotato.

Table 15 : Summary table of products and important characteristics

Product	Men's FGD	Women's FGD	Gogori	Liringo	Kafin-Chiri	Garun-Ali
Fried	Crispiness, Mealiness	Crispiness, Mealiness, sugary	X	X	X	X
Boiled	Mealiness	Mealiness	X	X	X	
Roasted		Sugary	X			
Dried		Mealiness				X

4 CONCLUSION

The study showed inhabitants of the communities involved in the study were predominantly Hausa and few Fulani pastoralists. The major livelihood activities in these communities were virtually the same, except Gogori where the community according to the leadership is well known in pots making, which was predominantly performed by females in this community. Fishing was a common livelihood activity in all these communities, which was due to the water bodies around these communities. The water bodies in addition to fishing support the production of sweet potato and other vegetable crops in the dry season. In terms of wealth categories, very poor and very wealthy individuals were generally low in all communities. There were similarities among the wealth categories in all the communities. However, there were also differences in those communities in the perceptions of men and women as individuals considered to be wealthy or moderately wealthy.

The most prevalent farming practice by men and women in Bagwai was monocropping while in Garko it was intercropping. Sweetpotato was ranked the most important crop in all the communities during the dry season. However in the rainy season, sorghum was deemed more important. Sweetpotato and maize were identified as important for income while millet and sorghum were for

home consumption. Sweetpotato was grown by at least 80% of the people sampled. More so, at least 70% of the sweetpotatoes grown in the communities were for sale. Activities involved in production of sweetpotato in these communities were gender- specific, for example women were mostly involved in planting the vines and harvesting.

The respondents indicated that they had accessed new sweetpotato varieties in the past 10-20 years; Gogori had received Dan-Izala, those in Liringo it was Dan-Madagali and Dan-Izala while for Garun-Ali it was the variety Dan Barnawa. The most common varieties grown at the time of the study were; Dan-Madagali, Dan-Izala, Dan-Bakalori, Dan-China, Dan-Barnawa and Dan-Batsari. The main causes of limited use of improved varieties in the communities were; no access to vines in subsequent years, late maturity, disease and pest attack and their lack of mealiness. Important characteristics of sweetpotato spanned agronomic, post-harvest, sensory and market attributes such as; mealiness, high yield, high price, big tubers and early maturity. Of highest importance to respondents in Gogori and Liringo was mealiness except for the Gogori men for whom high yield was top. More so, high yield and price were important for both men and women in Gogori. Big tubers were priority for men and women in Liringo. Early maturity was an important characteristic across the communities in Kafin-Chiki and Garun-Ali.

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